

SUB'YEKTIV VA SPORT

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Annotatsiya. Sport bugungi kunda ijtimoiy hayotning muhim qismidir. Sport tushunchasi jismoniy va ruhiy salomatlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash, o'ziga bo'lgan ishonch va ijtimoiylashuvni oshirish, hamjihatlikni ta'minlashdagi rolini ochib berish orqali o'zgacha ma'no kasb etdi. So'nggi yillarda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, sport jismoniy salomatlik bilan bir qatorda insonning psixologik salomatligiga ham ta'sir qiladi. Shaxsning psixologik salomatligi bilan bog'liq o'rganiladigan mavzulardan biri bu sub'ektiv farovonlikdir. Subyektiv farovonlik shaxsning subyektiv dunyosida; baxtli his qilish va o'zini ijobiy baholash. Biroq, sub'ektiv farovonlik sport psixologiyasi uchun yangi sohadir. Adabiyotda sub'ektiv farovonlik sportga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan va ta'sir qiladigan tadqiqot natijalari mavjud. Shunga asoslanib, ushbu tadqiqot adabiyotlar kontekstida sport va sub'ektiv farovonlik o'rtasidagi munosabatni ochib berishga harakat qildi. Tadqiqotning oxirgi qismida kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar uchun ba'zi takliflar berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sport, sub'ektiv farovonlik.

SUBJECTIVE AND SPORT

Abstract. Sport is an important part of social life today. The concept of sport gained a special meaning by revealing its role in supporting physical and mental health, increasing self-confidence and socialization, and ensuring unity. Researches conducted in recent years have shown that sports affect a person's psychological health as well as physical health. One of the research topics related to the psychological health of the individual is subjective well-being. Subjective well-being is in the subjective world of the individual; feeling happy and positive self-evaluation. However, subjective well-being is a new field for sport psychology. In the literature, there are research findings that subjective well-being affects and is affected by sports. Based on this, this study tried to reveal the relationship between sports and subjective well-being in the context of the literature. In the last part of the study, some suggestions for future research are given.

Keywords: Sport, subjective well-being.

СУБЪЕКТИВ И СПОРТ

Аннотация. Сегодня спорт является важной частью общественной жизни. Особое значение понятие спорта приобрело, раскрыв его роль в поддержании физического и психического здоровья, повышении уверенности в себе и социализации, обеспечении единства. Исследования, проведенные в последние годы, показали, что спорт влияет как на психологическое здоровье человека, так и на физическое. Одной из тем исследований, связанных с психологическим здоровьем личности, является субъективное благополучие. Субъективное благополучие находится в субъективном мире личности; чувство счастья и положительная самооценка. Однако субъективное благополучие — новая область спортивной психологии. В литературе имеются данные исследований о том, что на субъективное благополучие влияет и влияет спорт. Исходя из этого, данное исследование попыталось выявить связь между спортом и субъективным благополучием в контексте

литературы. В последней части исследования даются некоторые предложения для будущих исследований.

Ключевые слова: Спорт, субъективное благополучие.

KIRISH

Bir necha asrlar oldin paydo bo'lgan sport bugungi kunda ijtimoiy hayotning muhim qismiga aylandi. Sport tushunchasi shaxsning jismoniy va ruhiy salomatligini rivojlantirish, bo'sh vaqtdan unumli foydalanish, o'z-o'ziga ishonch, ijtimoiylashuv va hamjihatlikni ta'minlashdagi o'rnini tadqiq etish va ochib berish orqali o'zgacha ma'no kasb etdi. Sport va jismoniy salomatlik bo'yicha birinchi tadqiqotlar sportning jismoniy salomatlikka ta'sirini ta'kidladi va sportning yurak-qon tomir sog'lig'i, mushaklarning kuchi, chidamliligi, moslashuvchanligi va tana yaxlitligiga ijobiy ta'sirini aniqladi; So'nggi yillarda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, sport jismoniy salomatlik bilan bir qatorda insonning psixologik salomatligiga ham ta'sir qiladi.

Psixologik salomatlikning muhim ko'rsatkichlaridan biri shundaki, shaxs o'zining sub'ektiv dunyosida o'zini baxtli his qiladi va o'zini ijobiy baholaydi. Bu holat "sub'ektiv farovonlik" tushunchasi bilan ifodalangan bo'lib, u shaxsning hodisalarga munosabatini, hodisalarga va hukmlarga hissiy munosabatini ifodalaydi. Subyektiv farovonlik uchta o'lchovga ega: ijobiy ta'sir, salbiy ta'sir va hayotdan qoniqish. Ijobiy ta'sir; ishonch, qiziqish, umid, hayajon, g'urur, quvonch, salbiy ta'sir kabi his-tuyg'ular; Bu g'azab, nafrat, aybdorlik, qayg'u, tashvish kabi salbiy his-tuyg'ularni anglatadi va nihoyat hayotdan qoniqish o'lchovi sevgi, nikoh, do'stlik va o'yin-kulgiga tegishli. Shaxslar yoqimli his-tuyg'ularni his qilganda, qiziqarli mashg'ulotlar bilan shug'ullanganda, quvonchni boshdan kechirganda va o'z hayotidan mamnun bo'lganda yuqori sub'ektiv farovonlikni boshdan kechiradilar. Adabiyotlar o'rganilganda, sub'ektiv farovonlik tushunchasi bir nechta o'xshash tushunchalar bilan o'rganilganligi aniqlandi. Ijobiy psixologiyada shaxsning farovonligi bilan bog'liq ko'plab tushunchalar farovonlik, hayotdan qoniqish, hayot sifati va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi. kabi tushunchalar mavjudligi va shunga o'xshash xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan boshqa tushunchalar bir-birining o'rnida ishlatilishi kuzatiladi.

Nazariy kontekstda ko'rib chiqilsa, asosan Maqsad nazariyasi tomonidan izohlanadigan sub'ektiv farovonlik tushunchasi faoliyat, oqim, yuqoridan pastga, mulohaza yuritish, ijtimoiy taqqoslash, farovonlik doirasi va boshqalardan iborat. Kumulyativ tarzda rivojlanayotgan nazariyalar bilan izohlashga harakat qilinadi.

Shaxsning baxt-saodatini tadqiq etuvchi bu nazariyalar, asosan, shaxsning hayoti, dunyoqarashi va voqealarga baho berish bilan bog'liq. Biroq, tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, shaxsning psixologik salomatligi kuchli bo'lishi uchun faqat sub'ektiv farovonlik etarli emas. Riff va Keyes sub'ektiv farovonlik shaxsning psixologik jihatdan sog'lom bo'lishining yagona mezonini emasligini va sub'ektiv farovonlik bilan birga ba'zi xususiyatlar (ekologik ustunlik, shaxsiy o'sish va hayot maqsadi) ham talab qilinishi mumkinligini ta'kidlaydilar.

Hodisalarni o'z holicha idrok eta olmaydigan, boshqacha aytganda, ularga real baho bera olmaydigan kishilarning his-tuyg'ularidan xabardor bo'lishi mumkin emas. Bundan kelib chiqib, his-tuyg'ularidan bexabar bo'lgan shaxs o'zining baxtli ekanligini bildirsa ham, bu shaxsni to'liq psixologik sog'lom deb bo'lmaydi. Muxtasar qilib aytganda, sub'ektiv farovonlik psixologik salomatlik uchun zaruriy, ammo yagona shart emas.

SUB'YEKTIV SOVVONAT VA SPORT

Sportning shaxsning jismoniy va ma'naviy rivojlanishiga muhim ta'siri bor, deb hisoblashadi. Shaxs rivojlanishining dastlabki bosqichlaridan boshlab jismoniy mashqlar qilish inson hayotining har bir bosqichida ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Bolaligidanoq sport bilan shug'ullanish orqali o'zini taniy boshlagan shaxs o'smirlik davrida hayot uchun ba'zi maqsadlarni ishlab chiqadi, shuningdek, shaxsiy shaxsiyatini rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan sport mashg'ulotlari tufayli sub'ektiv farovonligini oshiradi. Unda aytilishicha, o'smirlarning hayotiy maqsadlarini aniqlash va strategiyalardan foydalanish tendentsiyalari ortishi bilan ularning sub'ektiv farovonlik darajasi oshadi. Hayotiy maqsadlarni aniqlash yoki strategiyalardan foydalanish ko'nikmalari sport faoliyati orqali shaxs erishishi mumkin bo'lgan ko'plab yutuqlardan biridir. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (1997) ruhiy farovonlik salomatlik holatini tashkil etuvchi boshqa o'lchovlarda muhim o'rin tutadi, deb ta'kidlaydi. va salomatlik nafaqat "kasalliklarning oldini olish".

Unda hech qanday vaziyat yo'qligi aytiladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, jismoniy faoliyat ko'plab sog'liq muammolarini (yurak ishemik kasalligi, semirish va boshqalar) kamaytiradi va hayot sifatini oshiradi. Diener (2000) ijtimoiy-madaniy omillar hayotdan qoniqishga ta'sir qiladi, turmush tarzini belgilaydi va hayotning ijobiy tomonlariga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. shaxsning salomatligi. Unda aytilishicha, jismoniy faollik yanada ijobiy hissiy holatni yaratadi va bu sub'ektiv farovonlikka ta'sir qiladi. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti hisobotida (2002) ta'kidlanishicha, sport mashg'ulotlarida ishtirok etish ijobiy psixologik ta'sir ko'rsatadi, tashvish va depressiyani kamaytiradi va ijtimoiy munosabatlar, ayniqsa sportga asoslangan, shaxsning psixologik farovonligini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

XULOSA VA TAVSIYALAR

Ushbu tadqiqotda shaxsning jismoniy va psixologik rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan sport bilan shaxs hayotini kognitiv va hissiy jihatdan baholash sifatida tavsiflangan sub'ektiv farovonlik tushunchasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik adabiyotlar kontekstida ochib berilgan. . Adabiyotlar o'rganilganda, sub'ektiv farovonlik tushunchasi va sport o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning ahamiyatini ochib beruvchi milliy va xalqaro tadqiqotlar mavjudligi ko'rinadi.

Ushbu tadqiqotlarda sportning shaxsning sub'ektiv farovonlik darajasiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi, shaxsning shaxslararo munosabatlarini mustahkamlashi, baxt va nekinlik tuyg'ularini rivojlantirishi aniqlangan. Ushbu tadqiqotlardan tashqari, adabiyotlarda ham tadqiqotlar mavjud. sub'ektiv farovonlikning sportga ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatib, sportning shaxslarning sub'ektiv farovonlik darajalariga ta'siridan farqli o'laroq. Ushbu tadqiqotlarda doimiy ravishda musobaqada bo'lgan sportchilar o'zlarini ham ta'sirchan, ham kognitiv jihatdan baholashlari ko'rsatilgan. , sub'ektiv farovonlikni oshirish, jismoniy faollik yanada ijobiy emotsional holatni yaratadi, sport mashg'ulotlarida qatnashish tashvish va tushkunlikni kamaytiradi va ijtimoiy munosabatlar, ayniqsa sportga asoslangan holda, shaxsning psixologik farovonligini oshiradi. vaziyatni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Ushbu barcha ma'lumotlarga qo'shimcha ravishda, tadqiqotchilar sub'ektiv farovonlik shaxsning psixologik salomatligining yagona mezoni emasligini, sub'ektiv farovonlik va ba'zi xususiyatlar (ekologik ustunlik, shaxsiy o'sish va hayotdagi maqsad) ham shaxsning sog'lig'iga ta'sir qilishini ko'rsatdi.

Sport insonning jismoniy va ruhiy salomatligi uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bundan tashqari, sport bilan shug'ullanadigan shaxslarning hayotda va sportda muvaffaqiyatga erishish istagini, shaxslararo munosabatlar ko'nikmalarini, baxt va optimizmni yaxshilashning yangi usullarini topish qobiliyatiga ega bo'lishini ta'minlash uchun o'quv dasturlari tashkil etilishi mumkin va shu bilan ularning sub'ektiv farovonligini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Shaxsning subyektiv farovonligini oshirishda oilaning yordami ham muhim ahamiyatga ega.

REFERENCES

1. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). FOCUS ON AEROBIC (LI) TYPE OF MOTOR ACTIVITY BASED ON FITNESS PROGRAMS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 81–90.
2. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). METHODS OF ORGANIZING NON-TRADITIONAL FITNESS CLASSES. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-09>
3. Yarasheva Dilnoza Ismail Qizi. (2023). TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(10), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue10-16>
4. Yarashova, D. (2023). THE IMPACT OF PLAYING SPORTS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 230–234. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24325>
5. Ярашева, Д. (2023, April). ФИТНЕС КАК ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 278-283).
6. Yarasheva, D. (2022). BOLALARDA MASHQ QILISHNING AHAMIYATI. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 19(1), 139-142.
7. Ярашева, Д. (2023). СТИЛИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ НЕТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 19(5), 6-10.
8. Yarashova, D. (2023). STRENGTH TRAINING AND STRENGTH TRAINING IN CHILDREN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 211-215.
9. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS, CULTURE AND SOCIETY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 152–163. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-17>
10. Azamat Orunbayev, (2023) NONUSHTANING MASHQ BAJARISHGA TA'SIRI. *International journal of scientific researchers* 2(2), 3-6.
11. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). USING TECHNOLOGY IN A SPORTS ENVIRONMENT. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-07>
12. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). FITNES VA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA MURABBIYLIK YO'NALISHIGA KONTSEPTUAL YONDASHUV. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(8), 23–28. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/431>

13. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). PANDEMIYA DAVRIDA MOBIL SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH VA FITNES DASTURLARI (PROGRAM). *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(7), 37–42. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/414>
14. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). A STUDY OF THE AGGRESSIVE STATUS OF FOOTBALL FANS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 73–80. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-10>
15. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). YEVROPA MAMLAKATLARIDA YUQORI MALAKALI FUTBOLCHI VA MURABBIYLARNI TEXNIK TAKTIK HARAKATLARINI TADBIQ QILISH METODIKASI. *THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH*, 2(14), 187-189.
16. Nuriddinov, A., Sayfiyev, H., & Sirojev, S. . (2023). WHY FOOTBALL IS THE FIRST SPORT THAT COMES TO MIND TODAY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 200–203. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24104>
17. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). THE ROLE OF FAIR PLAY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 244–250. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24327>
18. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). NIMA UCHUN FUTBOL BUGUNGI KUNDA SPORT DEB ATALGANIDA BIRINCHI NAVBATDA AQLGA KELADI.
19. Nuriddinov Axrorjon Bahodir o'g'li, (2023) Futbol zo'ravonligi, fanatizm va millatchilik *International journal of scientific researchers* 2(1), 451-456.
20. Saidova, M., & Sayfiyev, H. (2023). CONTENT-IMPORTANCE AND PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 192-199.
- 21. Saidova, M. (2023). CONTENT-IMPORTANCE AND PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 192-198.**
22. Sayfiyev, H., & Saidova, M. (2023). EFFECTS OF GYMNASTICS ON FUNDAMENTAL MOTOR SKILLS (FMS), POSTURAL (BALANCE) CONTROL, AND SELF-PERCEPTION DURING GYMNASTICS TRAINING. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 204-210.
- 23. Sayfiyev, H. (2023). EFFECTS OF GYMNASTICS ON FUNDAMENTAL MOTOR SKILLS (FMS), POSTURAL (BALANCE) CONTROL, AND SELF-PERCEPTION DURING GYMNASTICS TRAINING. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 204-210.**
24. Ayubovna, S. M., & Komiljonova, K. I. (2022). Features of Application of Sports Games in Preschool Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 16, 17-23.
25. Saidova, M., & Sayfiyev, H. (2023). CONTENT-IMPORTANCE AND PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 192-199.
26. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND WORKING METHODS OF COACHES. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 50–60. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-08>
27. Shoxrux, S. (2023). VOLEYBOLDA OTISH TEZLIGI TUSHUNCHASI VA AHAMIYATI. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(11), 913-917.

28. Sirojev, S. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF SHOOTING SPEED IN VOLLEYBALL. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 187-191.
29. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORTS AND LOGIC. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 97–106.
30. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). APPLICATIONS OF SPORT PSYCHOLOGY IN THE WORLD. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 107–120.
31. Sirojev, S. (2023). TEACHING ACTIVITIES AND PHILOSOPHY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 235–243.
32. Xayrulloevich, S. H. (2023). SPORT GIMNASTIKA MASHG'ULOTLARIDA ASOSIY HARAKAT QOBILYAT (FMS), POSTURAL (MUVOZANAT) NAZORAT VA O'ZINI O'ZI IDROK ETISHGA SPORT GIMNASTIKASINING TA'SIRI.
33. Saidova, M., & Sayfiyev, H. (2023). CONTENT-IMPORTANCE AND PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 192-199.
34. Sayfiyev, H., & Saidova, M. (2023). EFFECTS OF GYMNASTICS ON FUNDAMENTAL MOTOR SKILLS (FMS), POSTURAL (BALANCE) CONTROL, AND SELF-PERCEPTION DURING GYMNASTICS TRAINING. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 204-210.
35. Sirojev, S., Nuriddinov, A., & Sayfiyev, H. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF SHOOTING SPEED IN VOLLEYBALL. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 187-191.
36. Nuriddinov, A., Sayfiyev, H., & Sirojev, S. (2023). WHY FOOTBALL IS THE FIRST SPORT THAT COMES TO MIND TODAY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 200-203.
37. Сайфиев, Х., & Саидова, М. (2023). БАДМИНТОНИСТЫ ФИЗИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДГОТОВКА И ЕМУ РАЗРАБОТКА МЕТОДЫ. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(4), 45-54.
38. Xayrullayevich, S. H., & Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). BADMINTONCHILAR JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIGI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKALARI. *FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES*, 2(18), 201-208.
39. Nuriddinov, A., Sayfiyev, H., & Sirojev, S. (2023). WHY FOOTBALL IS THE FIRST SPORT THAT COMES TO MIND TODAY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 200-203.